

RESEARCH ON THE EVOLUTION OF WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS IN FISH PONDS DURING THE COLD SEASON IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract

The paper presents scientific data and information resulting from monitoring the most important water quality parameters in the pond during the cold season (November 2024 – March 2025), in order to assess the impact of climate change on aquatic ecosystems used for fish farming. The analysis focused on physical parameters (water temperature and turbidity) and chemical parameters (dissolved oxygen, salinity, pH, and nitrogen compounds), tracking variations specific to periods of low temperatures and their influence on fish wintering conditions. The results obtained highlight the major role of climate fluctuations in altering the ecological balance of fish ponds and emphasize the need to apply monitoring and adaptive management measures to maintain the productivity and sustainability of fish farming systems. Therefore, the physical parameters had average values between 3.35 and 10.65°C for water temperature, and turbidity fluctuated, with some occasional increases, but in general the values remained low. The values of the chemical parameters monitored showed relative stability of pH and high levels of dissolved oxygen ($\approx 9\text{--}10$ mg/L), nitrites (NO_2^-) and nitrates (NO_3^-) had low values, with no risk of toxicity, but ammonium (NH_4^+) showed moderate variations between ponds, within the limits accepted in aquaculture, indicating efficient management of mineralization processes. The warming trend in water temperature is a major challenge for the sustainability of aquaculture.

Keywords: *water quality, fishponds, cold season, climate change, dissolved oxygen, aquaculture sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the greatest current challenges for aquatic ecosystems, directly influencing the ecological balance and productivity of fish farming systems. In recent years, temperature changes, precipitation variations, and extreme phenomena associated with the cold season have put additional pressure on fish ponds, affecting water quality and, implicitly, fish health (D'Abramo and Slater, 2019; Choi et al., 2021). Water chemistry is influenced by precipitation at several levels, altering the balance of key physical and chemical indicators of water, nutrient loading, and gas exchange.

Aquaculture is directly dependent on the quality of the physical and chemical parameters of the water sources supplying fish ponds, among which water temperature plays an essential role, influencing fish metabolism, dissolved oxygen solubility, and the dynamics of chemical compounds in water (Vagner et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022). In our country, the temperature range of aquatic ecosystems falls within relatively narrow limits (-30°C, +40°C), resulting in water temperatures between +2°C and +30°C (Usafii et al., 2021; Wong & Candolin, 2015; Menon et al., 2023). Under the specific climatic conditions in Romania, the average water temperature in fish ponds during winter generally ranges between 2 and 5°C. During the cold season, the metabolic activity of fish decreases significantly, to a state of deep physiological rest, equivalent to hibernation. An increase in water temperature reactivates metabolic processes, which seriously disrupts the biological cycle of fish, affecting their metabolism and reproductive cycle, especially in species that synchronize their reproduction with seasonal temperatures (Ferreira et al., 2011; Volkoff and Rønnestad, 2020; Islam et al., 2022).

Water quality is the key factor in biological processes in fish ponds, and monitoring physical and chemical parameters is essential for maintaining a stable aquatic environment. During the cold season, lower temperatures and reduced photosynthetic processes can lead to a decrease in dissolved oxygen concentration, while the accumulation of nitrogen compounds can significantly affect fish metabolism (Teal et al., 2008; Galappaththi et al., 2020; Alfonso et al., 2021). Variations in pH, salinity, and turbidity can also influence biochemical processes and the trophic balance of the ecosystem. Precipitation can increase turbidity through soil erosion and suspended particles, reducing light penetration and photosynthesis. High turbidity can block fish gills and reduce primary productivity. In terms of water quality, for example, uneven temperature gradients profoundly influence fish behavior and shape their complex adaptations and responses aimed at optimizing survival strategies (Fu et al., 2018; Nadermann et al., 2019; Olesen et al., 2019).

In this context, the present study aims to analyze the evolution of the most important water quality parameters in fish ponds during the cold season, with a focus on the relationship between climatic factors and the stability of the aquatic environment. The results obtained provide a scientific basis for the adoption of adaptive management measures aimed at ensuring the sustainability and productivity of aquaculture systems in the context of climate change.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in fish ponds belonging to the Nucet Fish Farming Research and Development Station (SCDP Nucet), which covers an area of 167 ha of water surface, divided into approximately 90 ponds of different sizes and uses. Monitoring was carried out during the cold season, i.e. from November 2024 to the end of February 2025, with the aim of analyzing the most important water quality

parameters in order to assess the impact of climate change on the aquatic environment and the health of fish.

The ponds studied are located along the main channel of the Ilfov stream, downstream from the Ilfoveni reservoir (figure 1). Water is supplied by gravity from this stream, and the water used in aquaculture systems is discharged back into the same channel. During the wintering period, a minimum maintenance flow of 2–4 l/sec/ha was maintained to ensure adequate oxygenation and temperature conditions.

Figure 1. Description of the site – SCDP Nucet (source: <https://earth.google.com>)

The fish stock was harvested between November 10 and 15, 2024, and introduced for wintering in accordance with technological standards, in ponds of different sizes and depths, depending on their age and size. The depth of the wintering ponds ranges from 1.5 to 2.4 m.

The monitored parameters were divided into two categories:

- Physical parameters: water temperature and turbidity;
- Chemical parameters: dissolved oxygen, salinity, pH, and nitrogen compounds (ammonium, nitrites, nitrates).

Water samples were collected at the beginning and middle of each month in inert, high-density polyethylene (HDPE) containers from 20 points, that is 19 ponds and the water supply source, the Ilfov stream (Figure 2). A total of 200 water samples were collected between November 2024 and March 2025 and analyzed for quality parameters.

The air temperature was monitored daily, three times a day (at 8:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m., and 4:00 p.m.), at the local weather station located within the SCDP-Nucet perimeter.

In accordance with the recorded air temperature values, the temperature of the ponds was determined at the same times, as well as the dissolved oxygen content, which must be maintained at a minimum level of 5-6 mg/l.

The water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and saturation were determined using a portable *Hanna Instruments HI9829-11042* multiparameter meter (Hanna Ltd., Romania) equipped with GPS, and a turbidimeter was used to determine turbidity.

Figure 2. Overview of the experimental basins studied (Source: <https://earth.google.com>)

The pH was determined using a portable *Dostmann KLH9* pH meter (1.0-14 pH).

The concentration of nitrogen anion, nitrite anion, and ammoniacal nitrogen were determined in the laboratory using the spectrophotometric method (*Griess-Ilosvay* method). Alkalinity was determined in the laboratory using the volumetric method.

The collected data were statistically processed using descriptive and comparative analyses to highlight trends and variations in parameters in relation to the climatic conditions specific to the cold season. The results were presented in tables and graphs, facilitating the interpretation of the impact of climatic fluctuations on water quality and fisheries management.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The interpretation of the results obtained was carried out in accordance with the provisions of the “Standard for the classification of surface water quality”, correlated with data from the specialized literature in the field of water used for fishing (OMMGA No. 161/2006).

Water and air temperature values between November 2024 and March 2025 showed significant variations, with trends that can be correlated with seasonal climate changes (table 1).

Therefore, during the winter months (December-February), the average water temperature ranged between 3.35 °C and 5.24 °C, confirming the onset of the cold season. However, it should be noted that in January 2025, the average air temperature was 5.59 °C, higher than in December (4.51 °C), suggesting an atypically warmer period in the middle of winter.

Table 1. Average water and air temperatures between November 2024 and March 2025

MONTH	YEAR	Water temperature °C				Air temperature °C			
		Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard deviation
November	2024	4.4	14.1	7.03	±2.37	-2.0	20.0	6.41	± 3.51
December	2024	3.0	7.0	5.24	±1.05	-2.0	15.0	4.51	± 2.34
January	2025	2.5	6.5	4.55	±1.15	-6.5	17.2	5.59	±3.52
February	2025	1.5	6.5	3.35	±1.59	-10.0	12.0	0.44	±3.77
March	2025	4.5	14.8	10.65	±2.74	0	23.5	11.20	±4.12

In March 2025, the average water temperature reached 10.65°C and the average air temperature reached 11.20°C, with maximums of 14.8°C (water) and 23.5°C (air). These values are higher than expected for the end of the cold season, indicating early warming that may influence the biological cycle of fish species. The increase in temperatures during the transition months (November and March) signals a shortening of the cold season and a possible shift in the development and reproduction stages of fish species (figure 3).

Figure 3. Evolution of average temperatures during the cold season (November 2024–March 2025)

In conclusion, although December and February showed normal characteristics for the cold season, the values recorded in January and March highlight the warming trend and change in climate patterns, with possible implications for the ecological balance in the pond.

Chemical parameters of water

The analysis of water quality parameters in the studied ponds showed overall stability, with some differences between basins.

The average values and standard deviations for the parameters monitored showed moderate variations in water quality during the period analyzed. The parameters analyzed were: turbidity, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrites (NO_2^-), nitrates (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), and alkalinity (Table 2).

Table 2. Average values of the main parameters of pond water during the cold season

Parameters	MU	Average/ \pm STDEV
pH	pH units	7.00 \pm 0.30
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	mg/L	9.90 \pm 0.90
Nitrites (NO_2^-)	mg/L	0.04 \pm 0.01
Nitrates (NO_3^-)	mg/L	0.05 \pm 0.02
Ammonia (NH_4^+)	mg/L	0.55 \pm 0.15
Turbidity	FNU	5.5 \pm 3.0
Alkalinity	mg/L HCl 0,1N	2.70 \pm 0.50

- The pH remained stable around neutral (≈ 7), indicating water suitable for maintaining biological balance.

- Dissolved oxygen (DO) had high values (≈ 9 – 10 mg/L), suggesting good oxygenation of the experimental basins, which is essential for aquatic organisms.

- Nitrate and nitrite concentrations were low, confirming a low load of nitrogen compounds and a low risk of nitrate pollution.

- Ammonium (NH_4^+) levels varied moderately but remained within acceptable limits for aquatic environments, indicating effective management of mineralization processes.

- Moderate alkalinity reflects adequate buffering capacity, preventing sudden pH variations.

- Turbidity fluctuated, with some occasional increases, but values remained low overall, suggesting clear water with little suspended particulate matter (Table 3).

Table 3. Summary of values for the main water parameters in the analyzed ponds

Parameters	Value range (ponds)	General remarks
pH	6.94 – 7.19	Almost neutral, optimal for most fish species
Alkalinity (mg/L)	2.52 – 2.82	Moderate level, acting as a pH buffer.
Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	9.48 – 10.28	High and stable value, favorable for fish respiration.
Nitrites (mg/L)	0.03 – 0.07	Low value, no toxic risk.
Nitrates (mg/L)	0.04 – 0.08	Low value, characteristic of waters with controlled nutrient input.
Ammonia (mg/L)	0.36 – 0.79	In some ponds, it exceeds 0.7 mg/L → organic load.
Turbidity (FNU)	3.09 – 13.20	Large variations between basins, some waters more turbid.

- The pH is close to neutral (6.9–7.1), which is optimal for most fish species, avoiding both acidification and excessive alkalization.

- Alkalinity is maintained at moderate values (~2.5–2.8 mg/L), which contributes to good water buffering and prevents sudden pH variations.

- Dissolved oxygen is within high limits (9.5–10.3 mg/L), indicating good oxygenation, favorable for fish metabolism and nitrification processes.

- Nitrites and nitrates are at very low levels, indicating efficient oxidation processes and a lack of significant nutrient pollution.

- Ammonia varies between basins; in general, the values are acceptable, but some exceed the threshold of 0.7 mg/L, which can affect the sensitivity of fish species and indicates an accumulation of organic matter.

- Turbidity varies considerably between basins (3–13 FNU). More turbid waters can reduce light penetration and, implicitly, phytoplankton productivity, but the values do not exceed critical levels for fish farming.

Overall, the results indicate that most basins have good water quality for fish growth, but continuous monitoring of ammonium and turbidity is essential to prevent imbalances (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Comparison of minimum and maximum values for water quality parameters (November 2024 - March 2025)

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the physical and chemical parameters of the water in the studied fish ponds, correlated with the air and water temperature regime during the investigated period, highlights the fact that aquatic ecosystems are directly influenced by climate change and local environmental factors. Temperatures higher than the usual average for the winter months suggest a warming trend that could substantially alter the seasonal cycle of fish species, influencing fundamental processes such as reproduction, growth, and survival. According to the recorded data, i.e., winter season or wintering period 2024 - 2025 had about 130 days.

The relative stability of pH and high levels of dissolved oxygen demonstrate an aquatic environment favorable to metabolism and maintenance of trophic balance, while low, but variable concentrations of nitrogen compounds and fluctuating turbidity reflect complex processes of mineralization and circulation of organic matter, with potential effects on primary productivity. The alkalinity and buffering capacity of the water support the system's resistance to sudden pH variations, which is an essential factor for ecosystem stability.

The results indicate that the monitored parameters remain within the general safety limits for fish growth, but the effects of the warming trend on the water temperature regime pose a major challenge to the sustainability of aquaculture.

Monitoring essential water parameters, including temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, ammonia (NH₃), nitrites (NO₂⁻), and turbidity, is vital to ensuring optimal

habitat conditions. Low temperatures reduce fish metabolic rates and food intake, while the risk of oxygen depletion under ice cover increases, potentially leading to hypoxic stress and winter mortality. In addition, the accumulation of toxic compounds such as ammonia and nitrites can occur due to limited biological filtration during winter. The implementation of fundamental management strategies, such as aeration systems and ice management techniques, can reduce risks during winter. This study highlights the importance of accurate monitoring of pond water quality during fish species overwintering to minimize mortality and ensure species resilience under challenging environmental conditions.

Therefore, the data obtained highlights the need for integrated fisheries management that takes into account both current environmental conditions and climate trends in order to ensure the long-term viability and productivity of fish farms.

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